

The Motivation of Women Traders in Improving the Family Welfare (Study Case: Vendors at Pasar Gede Surakarta)

Aberona Thea Chenarani Surasno¹, Dwi Prasetyani², Bhimo Rizky Samudro³

^{1,2,3} Postgraduate Program of Economics and Development Studies, Sebelas Maret University

ABSTRACT: This paper aims to describe the motivation of women traders in improving family welfare in Surakarta. It employs a descriptive method to estimate data and information. Some factors including age, working hours, and duration of trade are investigated through the analysis. The result shows the average female traders work as a trader for 27 years. They formerly help parents then continue business man old or open alone. For starting traders, alone have reason. To fulfill needs, want to forward and because of coercive circumstances. Family always supports them as merchants, with arrangement adjusting time. For balance between work and the affairs House ladder, they get up more morning to finish the affairs house ladder or do it after selling on the market.

KEYWORDS: Family Welfare, Vendors, Women Traders.

INTRODUCTION

Surakarta city or more known as the city of Solo is a city that has various activities good the field of political, economic, social, and cultural. Besides that, Surakarta City is known as city trade, p This is marked by many activities trading both scale small, medium, and big.

Amount residents working in Surakarta City in 2015 reached 243,152 or 47.67% of the whole residents of Surakarta City. Resident working women reach several 43.41% of those working. In 2016 it reached 271,199 or 47.67% of the whole residents of Surakarta City. Resident working women reach a figure of 122,187 people. Amount residents who worked in 2017 of 259,304 and 45.65% of them were manifold sex girls. Enhancement occurred in 2018 with 259,465 people working or 50.1% of the total population in Surakarta.

Surakarta City residents who voted to become trader experience fluctuation every year. Amount residents to be traders in 2015 as many as 1456 people consisting from trader large 32 inhabitants, traders middle 207 and traders small 1217. In 2016 the number of residents to be traders was as many as 1400. In 2017 it was 1170 and in 2018 it was 655.

Big Market Hardjonagoro is the biggest market and feature characteristic of Surakarta City. This market's own building is interesting Because combines draft architecture Java-Europe artificial 1930. Traditional markets become a center gathering society in the past. Traditional markets own function as room economy, space social, and space culture. This _ is because the public can do activities sell buy, interact and earn learning from a market.

Its existence as a traditional market and tourist market opens opportunities particularly in the informal sector to traders. Traders are people with relatively varied capital who are trying in the field of production and sales of goods or services To fulfil the need group certain in society. Amount traders at the Pasar Gede as many as 368 traders who have Placement Rights Letters (SHP) for Los/ Kiosks in the Market. Besides That, there are also traders who do not own the right placement or they only sell in the yard.

The role of women in the public sector, especially in the field of trading the more increased. One of them is the involvement of women in the trade sector that is as traders selling in traditional markets. On the whole 60% of traders in the big market are dominated by traders Woman ie 222 traders. This is interesting for research that is for now trader motivation _ Women do activity economy as well as big contribution Pasar Gede Woman Trader to Economy His family.

RESEARCH METHODS

Study This held at Pasar Gede Hardjonagoro Surakarta City. Study this use method qualitative with analysis descriptive, purposeful For know in a manner descriptive from Motivation of Women Traders in increasing the family economy. Data used in the study This was obtained direct from the field with method of interview nor observation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overview of Pasar Gede Surakarta

Big Market is one _ legacy kingdom Mataram. This market is by Herman Thomas Karsten with the use of architecture Javanese-Colonial. Traditional market. This is given Big Market name Because consists of a big roof. Big Market consists of two separate buildings. _ Each consists of two floors. In 1928 Pasar Gede built by the Dutch Government over the initiative Sinuhun Nail Buwono X. Development of this market succeed resolved 1930. Big market experienced several renovations _ a consequence the damage suffered such as the fire tragedy 2000 years ago. Then on December 29, 2001 Pasar Gede was inaugurated by Governor Mardiyanto. kindly Gede market geography is located in the Village Sudiroprajan , district Jebres , to be precise across from Surakarta City Hall. Stall area in Pasar Besar many kinds of start from 2m² until with 40m² and 2 m² los until with 9m²

Type merchandise traded in this Market is Fruit / Wholesale Fruits, vegetables, Grabah, Wade, Grabadan, Meat Chicken, Meat Beef, Pork, Fish, Food typical Solo and others.

Characteristics Female Traders at Pasar Gede Surakarta

1. Age

Age be one _ matter important related to motivating somebody to do something thing (activity trading). The assumption someone who is old and productive has a trend of high motivation at work. Working Women Traders own aged between 22-80 years.

Table 1. Age Respondent Female Traders

No	Age	Amount	Percentage
1	20-<30	1	2
2	30-<40	7	14
3	40-<50	13	26
4	50-<60	15	30
5	60-<70	11	22
6	70-<80	2	4
7	>80	1	2

Based on the table can is known that amount respondents aged 20-29 years and over _ from 80 years by 1 person (2%). Merchant Woman who owns aged 30-39 years as many as 7 people (14%), aged 40-49 years as many as 13 people (26%), who have aged 50-59 years as many as 15 people (30%), who have aged 60-69 years as many as 11 people (22%), who have aged 70-79 years as many as 2 people (4%).

2. Working Hours

In the informal sector such as trading generally working society _ No own bond time in work, so time spent by traders _ One with other No same. Following table amount Female Traders trading in Pasar Gede.

Table 2. Working Hours Trade Respondent Female Traders

No	Working hours/day	Amount	Percentage
1	0-<5	5	10
2	5-<10	39	78
3	10-<15	6	12
4	15-<20	0	0

Pasar Gede Woman Trader start activity selling at 03.00 WIB until 16.00 WIB. Naturally, every trader is different from the others. Traders who use time 0-4 hours per day as many as 5 traders (10%), for 5-9 hours per day as many as 39 (78%), and who use 10-14 hours for selling as many as 6 people (12%).

3. Duration Trade

Par3a Women Traders in Pasar Gede have a different time in starting their efforts duration trading in the Market can become an Experience for Traders. Experience is activities carried out in a manner Keep going continuously on one field profession so that someone said an expert in the field.

Table 3. Trading Time Respondent Female Traders

No	Trading Time	Amount	Percentage
1	0-<10	5	10
2	10-<20	8	16
3	20-<30	12	24
4	30-<40	14	28
5	40-<50	6	12
6	>50	5	10

Based on the table on can is known amount trader woman who has experience trading for 0-9 years as many as 5 people (10%), traders woman who has experience for 10-19 years with as many as 8 people (16%), traders woman who has experience for 20-29 years as many as 12 people (24%), traders who own experience for 30-39 years as many as 14 people (28%), traders woman who has experience for 40-49 years as many as 6 people (12%) and traders woman who has experience over 50 years as many as 5 people (10%). The amount Woman trading merchants for more than 30 years because they start efforts from business family down decreased.

Analysis Motivation of Women Traders Trade

Women in essence geared towards improving position, role, ability, independence as well as mental and spiritual resilience in order to become partners parallel a man who is in harmony, compatible and balanced, as part not inseparable from effort enhancement quality source Power human. Woman Trader in Pasar Gede own some possible reasons seen in the table below this:

Table 4. Reason Merchant Girl started Trade

No	Starting a business	Amount	Percentage
1	Forward Parents	33	66 %
2	Starting Yourself	17	34 %

The Pasar Gede woman who started it business was down from Parents _ as many as 33 people (66%) while the women traders who started it Alone business traded as many as 17 people (34%). this _ shows that the majority of women traders only had forward businesses run by their family before, meanwhile, for Women Traders who are starting out Alone own Lots of reasons like circumstances that prompted them to work and only trade that can he do. Besides that, condition, flexible and non-flexible trading is bound to be one of the merchant reasons and women start their efforts. As a woman who has Lots not quite enough answer home, settings time to do job House before or after activity trading on the market is done.

Analysis to Improvement of Family Economy

Analysis This is the results obtained by the Women Traders during business trade during a day nor a month, which later results in income the used help or add need House ladder Trader Woman alone. Average income net earned by Pasar Gede Women Traders IDR 100,000.00 up to with IDR 300,000.00 per day or IDR 3,000,000.00 up to with IDR 9,000,00.00 per month.

Table 5. Member Working Family

No	Family	Amount	Percentage
1	Working Husband	37	74%
2	Husband Not Working	10	20%
3	Trading with Husband	2	4%
4	Not married yet	1	2%

Besides that, no denied member of another working family finally gives portion alone in enhancement economy family. Pasar Gede women traders who own husbands Work as many as 37 people (74%). this _ shows that income is only an adder or help enhancement economy family. Whereas Trader women who don't own working husbands as many as 10 people (20%), p the show role as a Bone back family as well as income earned _ Woman Trader become income main in the economy family. Merchants women in Pasar Gede also work the open business together with their husband as many as 2 people (4%), showed that their role as a trader only help the husband so that income earned is result of business together husband. Merchant women who still Not yet family by 1 person (2%).

CONCLUSION

Of the 50 women market traders in the big market own ages 22 to with 80 years.

Type traded commodity _ many kinds of start from Fruits, Vegetables, Grabah,, Wade, Grabada , Various type Meat , Fish as well food dried which is a typical souvenir of Solo.

The average female traders work as trader for 27 years. They formerly help parents

Then continue business man old or open alone. For starting trader, alone have reason. For fulfill need, want to forward and because of coercive circumstances. Family always support them as merchant, with arrangement adjusting time. For balance between work and affairs House ladder they get up more morning for finish affairs house ladder or do it after selling on the market.

REFERENCES

1. Bachtiar Suryo Bawono , Bambang Santosa . The Dual Role of Women in the Family Economy (Study The Case of Female Traders in Klewer Market). Journal of Development and Social Change, Vol. 3, No. 1, April 2020 p-ISSN 2614-5766, <https://jurnal.uns.ac.id/jodasc>
2. Brunetta R. Wolfman. The Role of Women: How Become Capable and Balanced in Various Roles. Yogyakarta: Kanisius
3. Aaron, Irhayati . Rifqoh . Super Woman: Success on the Spot Work and Family . Yogyakarta: ANDI Offset.
4. Irwan Abdullah, ed . Doubt Gender Paran . Yogyakarta: Student Offset Library.
5. Kadek Della Andriani * Ni Putu Martini Dewi. The Role of Balinese Women in
6. Increase Income House Ladder Through Sale of Upakara Facilities (Study Case Traders of Upakara Facilities in Badung Market). E- Journal of Development Economics, Udayana University , [Sl], oct. 2014. ISSN 2303-0178.
7. Nabila Shadrina , M. Faisal Akbar. Influencing Factors _ Income Women Workers in the Informal Trade Sector in the City of Pangkal Pinang. Klassen, Journal Economics and Development planning . Vol. 1, No. 2, 2021.
8. Raidayani , Rina Syafitri , Jelliani , Lisa instinct . Analysis Contribution Housewife Income _ Ladder (Study Case : Trader Vegetable) Against Income Family at Seumayam Market Subdistrict Darul Makmur Regency Nagan Raya . Journal Farming Business Vol 5, No 2, December 2019 ISSN 2477-3468 . Teuku University Umarpp . 65- 75 .
9. Ratna Saptari . 1997. Working women and change social : a introduction studies girl . Jakarta: Main Library of Graffiti
10. Siti Hariti Sastriyani. 2008. Women in the Public Sector (Women in the Public Sector). Yogyakarta: Center Gadjah Mada University Women's Studies and Tiara Wacana .
11. Sri Endah Nurhidayati . Profile Position and Role of Women in the Economic Sector , Health and Family Planning in Gresik Regency , journal health society , vol.1 no. 3, July 1999, p.31

Cite this Article: Aberona Thea Chenarani Surasno, Dwi Prasetyani, Bhimo Rizky Samudro (2023). The Motivation of Women Traders in Improving the Family Welfare (Study Case: Vendors at Pasar Gede Surakarta). International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(5), 2887-2890